

Research on the Intangible Cultural Heritage: Musical Culture of Hebei Local Opera “Dizi Diao”

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Abstract

The flute tune, also known as Guanzuo tune, is an ancient local opera genre passed down in Guanzuo Village, Rao Yang County, Hengshui City, Hebei Province, China. It was named after the flute, which was the main playing instrument in the early stage of its formation. During the Zhengde period of the Ming Dynasty, the flute tune was taught to the village children by a private school teacher who taught in Guanzuo Village, and it has been sung to this day. Flute tune singing high, men and women with the same cavity in the same tune, witty and humorous language, singing lining words, false words more, unique repertoire, rich in local characteristics, once loved by the people of Hengshui Rao Yang area.

Introduction

The flute tune is a small folk opera passed down in the Hengshui area of Hebei Province, which is isolated and has a small audience, and its historical heritage is rather tumultuous, so unlike Beijing opera, Kunqu and other nationwide operas that have received extensive attention from the academic community, there is a relative lack of literature and research results on the flute tune. In the process of reviewing the relevant literature, the author has paid special attention to the Luo Luo cavity because it is a local genre of the Luo Luo cavity.

Although it has been passed down for hundreds of years, it is rarely known to outsiders and has been neglected by cultural workers and theoretical researchers, so there is a relative lack of research data.

In this paper, we examine the musical culture of the flute tune based on literature, field research, and theories related to anthropology, ethnology, culture, and musicology. This paper focuses on four aspects: the historical origin of the flute tune, its historical heritage and development status, its musical and artistic characteristics, and its social function and value.

In the section of historical tracing, this chapter mainly uses the method of documentary evidence to analyze the relationship between the flute tune and the three origins of the Luo Luo cavity to further reveal the significant kinship between the flute tune and the northern string cavity and to clarify the historical origin of the Luo Luo cavity to which it belongs. In the section on historical transmission and development, this chapter mainly uses oral history and documentary and historical data to sort out, analyze and verify the history of the production and transmission of the flute tune in the Hengshui area, and investigate the current development of the flute tune association, so as to have a clearer development of the transmission of the flute tune; in the section on musical and artistic characteristics, this chapter mainly focuses on the flute tune's board style, the music of the song, the accompaniment band (accompaniment instruments, accompaniment characteristics) and the performance program (role system). In the section on social functions, this chapter focuses on the moral and ethical values of the patriarchal society, entertainment and folk rituals, artistic and aesthetic values, as well as the historical changes in promoting the spirit of the times, inheriting traditional culture and regional cultural identity values of the flute.

Analysis of the changing times of the value of the social function of the flute tune in the historical construction. In the above four chapters, the author draws on the triple analysis model of "concept-behavior-sound" in music anthropology, and combines "historical construction", "social maintenance", and "social identity", In the above four chapters, the author draws on the triple analysis model of "concept-behavior-sound" in music anthropology, and incorporates three dimensions of "historical construction", "social maintenance," and "individual creation and experience" to form an interactive and mutually feedback whole, thus revealing the musical and cultural connotations of the flute tune.

Literature on Flute Tunes

The literature on the flute tune is mainly found in some opera monographs, local chronicles and compilations of local opera materials; the academic research results are only available in a master's thesis (Lei reputation, 2015), and since then, the academic research on the flute tune has basically been blank, with only a short report published in the press aiming to call the attention of the community to the development of the flute tune in Guanzao village and to save the survival of the flute tune. report (Li Xiaoguo, 2017).

The historical origin of the flute tune.

The Editorial Committee of the Dictionary of Chinese Opera Types (1995), the Editorial Committee of the Chinese Opera Music Integration - Hebei Volume (1999), the Editorial Committee of the Chinese Opera Journal-Hebei Volume (1999), the Local History Compilation Committee of Hebei Province (2001), the Local History Compilation Committee of Rao Yang County (1998), the Editorial Department of the Opera Journal of the Cultural Bureau of the Hengshui District Administration (1986), and Lei reputation (2015) have all briefly introduced the historical origin of the flute tune. The core viewpoint of the above documents is basically the same, that is, the flute tune is an alias of Luo Luo cavity, also known as Guan Zuo tune, because at the early stage of its formation, the flute is the main instrument, "flute tune" is thus named; flute tune in Ming Zhengde years, by a private school teacher in Guan Zuo village, passed on to the local children's association, sung to this day. The historical origin of the flute tune is basically discussed by Lei (2015), which is similar to the above-mentioned literature. I expect to enrich and add to it by further examination in the thesis, which already provides a historical reference for this paper.

The musical and artistic characteristics of the flute tune.

The main focus of the literature on the musical and artistic characteristics of the flute tune is on the music of the singing voice, the accompanying instruments, and the traditional repertoire of the flute tune. The editorial committee of the Chinese Opera Dictionary (1995), the editorial committee of the Chinese Opera Music Integration - Hebei Volume (1999), the editorial department of the Cultural Bureau of the Hengshui District Office of Opera (1986), and Lei reputation (2015) have all introduced and discussed the singing music of the flute tune. The above-mentioned literature has provided either complicated or brief descriptions of the types of flute singing music and the types of tunes, and their basic views are consistent.

Lei's (2015) discussion of cantorial music is based on the above-mentioned literature, and the characteristics of the do bai of the flute tune have been described through field investigations. Accompanying instruments. The Editorial Committee of the Dictionary of Chinese Opera Types (1995), the Editorial Committee of the Chinese Opera Music Integration-Hebei Volume (1999), the Editorial Department of the Opera Journal of the Cultural Bureau of the Hengshui District Administration (1986) and Lei reputation (2015) have all documented research on the accompanying instruments of flute tunes. The core view of the relevant literature is that the accompaniment band of the flute tune is divided into Wenchang and Wuchang; at the early stage of the formation of the flute tune, the accompaniment instrument is a single wind instrument combination with the flute as the main instrument, and afterwards, under the influence of Hebei Bangzi, string instruments are added; the instrumentation of Wuchang is almost similar to that of Hebei Bangzi. Based on this basic view, Lei reputation (2015) clearly listed the number of different musical instruments in Wenchang and Wuchang through field surveys.

Traditional repertoire.

The Editorial Committee of the Dictionary of Chinese Opera Genres (1995), the Editorial Committee of the Chinese Opera Music. The traditional repertoire of the flute tune has been introduced by the Editorial Committee of the Chinese Opera Music Integration-Hebei Volume (1999), the Local History Compilation Committee of Hebei Province (2001), the Local History Compilation Committee of Rao Yang County (1998), the Editorial Department of the Cultural Bureau of the Hengshui District Office of Opera (1986), and Lei Reputation (2015). Each of the above-mentioned literature has its own focus on the traditional repertoire of the flute tune, and the number of repertoire involved varies. Lei Reputation (2015) provides a more detailed introduction to the traditional repertoire of the flute tune and, on this basis, classifies the repertoire and indicates when the different repertoires were performed.

In addition to the above research on the three main aspects of the musical art features of the flute tune, namely, the music of the singing voice, the accompanying instruments, and the traditional repertoire, the editorial committee of the Chinese Opera Dictionary (1995) provides a brief introduction to the performance program of the flute tune; Lei (2015) introduces the roles of the flute tune on the basis of a field survey, making the research richer. The existing theories on the artistic characteristics of the flute tune have laid a certain theoretical foundation for this thesis, but I believe that there is still room for further advancement on the basis of Lei's

richer existing research results. The existing research on the musical body of the flute tune lacks the analysis of example scores to support the study, and does not form a systematic study of "meter, tune, score and instrument". In particular, the development and revitalization of the flute tune has not been discussed by the Flute Tune Association in the 21st century.

Literature on the Luo Luo cadence

In the process of reviewing the literature on Luo Luo cavity, I found that only a few documents have been written on the distribution of the origin of Luo Luo cavity, and the research on Luo Luo cavity is mainly focused on the old Shanxi opera "Lingqiu Luo Luo cavity", which was officially approved as the first batch of national intangible cultural heritage by the State Council in 2006.

The origin and distribution of the Luo Luo cavity.

The editorial committee of the Chinese Opera Journal - Hebei Volume (1999), the editorial department of the Chinese Music Dictionary (2016), and Lei's reputation (2015) have documented the distribution of the origin of the Luoluo cantata, but with different views. The Editorial Board of Chinese Opera - Hebei Volume (1999) records that the Luo Luo cavity is an older type of opera and is related to the silk string cavity in Hebei, which is popular in the Yanbei region of Shanxi, and the silk string is also called Luo Luo cavity; the Editorial Department of Chinese Music Dictionary (2016) introduces the entry of Luo Luo cavity, which is an opera cavity and is related to the high cavity, and was popular in many areas in the Qing Dynasty. many regions, but it was lost much later. Lei reputation (2015)

The origin of the Luo Luo cadence is taken from the viewpoint of the editorial committee of the Chinese Opera Journal - Hebei Volume (1999). Through the above literature, I believe that the source of the Luo Luo cadence is ambiguous in the literature, and I hope to develop a clear view on the distribution of the source of the Luo Luo cadence through further research in this study, so as to prove the connection between the flute tune and it.

Research data on the Lingqiu Luo Luo cadence

There is a wealth of scholarly information on the Lingqiu Luo Luo cadence genre, mainly focusing on the following aspects:

The historical origin and transmission history of Lingqiu Luo Luo cavity. An Fang (2016) identifies the historical origin of Lingqiu Luo Luo cavity; Hu Xiang (2010) explores the relationship between the Luo Luo cavity and the Yiyang cavity and the string cavity of the Ming dynasty through the comparison of the singing voice, tune and accompaniment; and introduces the development of the three stages of the historical inheritance of the Luo Luo cavity: the rise, the flourishing and the decline.

The musical and artistic characteristics of Lingqiu Luo Luo cavity. An Fang (2016) studied the performance system, vocal system, and performance script of Lingqiu Luoluo cadence; Hu Xiang (2010) introduced the musical characteristics of the singing voice, tune, and accompaniment of Luoluo cadence; Liu Zhengang (2016) conducted an in-depth study on the types of singing tune, orchestra establishment, singing repertoire, singing characteristics, and performance characteristics of Lingqiu Luoluo cadence; Duan Wenying (2018) conducted an in-depth study on the musical characteristics of Lingqiu Luoluo cadence. Jiao Chunmei (2015) discusses the typical artistic characteristics of the Lingqiu Luo Luo cadence that have been developed over a long period of time and have an ancient cultural lineage, namely, the rhyming of the lyrics, the dialectal nature of the language, the support of the accompaniment, the structure of the cantata, the unique high eight-vocals, and the unique "back-gong sound" and "back-gong sound". "Anna Zhang and Penglong Wang (2012) focus on the unique cultural characteristics of the Luo Luo cadence in the process of development, i.e., the unique stage steps, the original country voice, and the drama that is both solemn and harmonious. The research on the cultural characteristics of the music and art of Lingqiu Luo Luo cavity accounts for a large proportion of the literature.

The heritage development of Lingqiu Luo Luo cavity. Deng Jiali (2015) proposes new ideas on the inheritance development of Luoluo cavity through the large modern drama "Village Judge" created and rehearsed by the Luoluo cavity troupe, and discusses the inheritance value of combining Luoluo cavity opera with campus culture; Liu Zhengang (2016) proposes multiple approaches for the future development of Lingqiu Luoluo cavity, including "strengthening the construction of the troupe itself, drawing on the development model of two-person opera, and powerfully promoting it in various ways. Liu Zhengang (2016) put forward feasible suggestions for the future development of Lingqiu Luo Luo chuan from multiple perspectives, such as "strengthening the construction of the troupe itself, learning from the development model of two-person opera, and powerful propaganda in various ways.

The research results of Lingqiu Luoluo cavity have been published by other scholars, so I will not list them here. The old Shanxi opera "Lingqiu Luoluo cavity" and the flute tune belong to the same Luoluo cavity. The above-mentioned research results on the historical origin, musical and cultural characteristics, and inheritance and

development of Lingqiu Luo Luo cavity provide a rich theoretical reference and basis for this paper to study the historical inheritance and artistic characteristics of the flute tune.

Theoretical foundation

In this thesis, the author intends to draw on the relevant theories of fusion cultural anthropology to investigate the musical The cultural connotation of the flute tune will be studied. In this paper, I will draw on the "holistic" and "functionalist" views of cultural anthropology and integrate them into my research. In this paper, we will draw on the "holistic" and "functionalist" viewpoints of cultural anthropology, and consider culture as a whole, so that the study of any cultural element should be placed in the context of the overall culture. The study of any cultural element should be understood in the context of the culture as a whole, and should not be studied in isolation from other cultural elements. Music as an important part of culture As an important part of culture, the attitude towards music art will not be regarded as a "pure art" independent of the forest of culture. The art of music, as an important part of culture, should not be treated as a "pure art" independent of culture, but rather as a more cultural In his approach to music art, he does not regard it as a "pure art" independent of culture, but rather focuses on discovering and examining its symbiosis with other cultural subsystems, with a more cultural character, and puts his research in a holographic perspective of multidimensional and systematic observation. In order to The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between music and human beings and the cultural context of music. The study of ethnomusicology is a multi-dimensional and systematic perspective. In the field of ethnomusicology, Alan P. Merriam, an important representative of the anthropological school of thought, has proposed "an understanding of the cultural context of music. In the field of ethnomusicology, Alan P. Merriam, an important representative of the anthropological school, proposed "the study of music in culture" (1960), "the study of music as culture" (1973), and "the study of music as culture" (1973). The study of music as culture" (1973), based on the traditional methodological categories of cultural anthropology, places music in the context of cultural facts and extends music to The study of music as culture" (1973) is based on the traditional methodological scope of cultural anthropology, which places music in the context of cultural facts and extends music to cultural categories related to human behavior and perceptions. A concise triple analysis model is devised: "concept-behavior-sound" (conceptualization of music, music-related behavior, music itself). Understanding Music as a Culture The semantics of music is no longer a matter of the sound itself, but rather a matter of the relationship between concept, act and music. The answer is to be found in the relationship between concept, act and music. "Concept, act, and sound" are an inseparable whole. All three exist simultaneously in musical performance. Merriam's threefold model of analysis established the "anthropological school" (musical anthropology).

Merriam's triple analysis model laid the foundation for the "anthropological" (musical anthropology) model of analysis, which became the classic research model. Later, the scholar Timothy Rice (Timothy Rice further elaborated on Merriam's model, and defined "historical composition, social maintenance, individual application and experience" anthropological framework with Merriam's "concept-act-voice" triple Merriam's "conceptual-behavioral-phonological" triad of analysis is combined. Merriam's and Rice's modes of analysis provide important insights for the author's research on this topic. In this paper, I hope to be able to provide the author with some insights into this topic.

In this paper, I hope to trace the origins of the flute genre, to clarify the historical origin of the Lolo cadence to which it belongs, and to explore the musical art of the flute. In this paper, I hope to trace the origins of the flute genre, to clarify the historical origins of the Luo Luo cadence to which it belongs, and to investigate what musical and artistic characteristics of the flute are directly related to the origins of the Luo Luo cadence. The history of the flute tune is examined and its development status is investigated and researched, with the aim of discovering the history of the flute tune since its formation in Rao Yang County during the Ming dynasty. The purpose of this study is to discover the supporting information about the development of the flute tune in Rao Yang County during the Ming Dynasty until the 1950s, and to The purpose of this study is to find out the evidence of the development of the flute tune in Hengshui Rao Yang County from the Ming dynasty to the 1950s. The above is a clearer picture of the development of flute tunes. The above discussion will be based on the "historical construction" of the flute tune. The above discussion is based on the "Historical Construction" section of the flute tune. In this paper, we analyze and study the musical and artistic characteristics of the flute tune, such as the characteristics of the singing voice The paper analyzes the musical and artistic characteristics of the flute tune, such as the characteristics of the singing voice, modal features, performance procedures, and the accompanying orchestra, in order to reveal the common features of the Luo Luo cavity and the unique characteristics of the The interpretation of the musical characteristics is inseparable from the performers. The interpretation of the artistic characteristics of the music is inseparable from the performers, and in this section we will analyze and explain the "personal creativity and experience" of the artists. With the change of the times, the development of society, the modernization the development of society and the intensification of the modernization process, the author needs to re-examine and explore the cultural value of the flute tune in modern

The cultural value of the flute tune in modern society, highlighting the changing times in the historical construction of the social function of the flute tune. In this section, it is the functional value of the flute that has been "socially maintained" that has allowed the flute to exist. The four parts of the discussion above are: In the above four parts of the discussion, the author has put three dimensions of the three dimensions throughout the analysis, so that they form a mutually integrated, interactive, and mutually feedback whole, and in the process of analysis, the author draws on the triple analysis model of "concept-behavior-acoustics" in music anthropology to reveal the role of the flute tune as a traditional Chinese opera. In the analysis, the authors will draw on the triple analysis model of "concept-act-acoustics" in music anthropology to reveal the musical and cultural connotations of the flute tune as a cultural heritage of traditional Chinese opera.

Local opera is an important part of local culture. The growth of any opera genre is a combination of its own internal development and external social and cultural forces. The growth of any opera genre is the result of the combined forces of its own internal development and external social and cultural forces. In this regard, it is important to examine the resources, environment, state, and laws of the existence and development of local opera art by applying the theories of cultural anthropology. To conduct a comprehensive, holistic and systematic study of the folkloric opera genre Dizi Tun and its cultural environment, revealing the cultural basis of the flute genre, break through the general description and artistic aesthetic study of the flute genre, and focus on the special artistic form of the flute genre and its profound artistic form. The study of the cultural foundations of the flute genre will break through the general description of the genre and the artistic aesthetic research, and develop a comprehensive, extensive, complete and in-depth research perspective on the special artistic form and profound cultural connotation of the genre. The study of flute tunes is not limited to the content, form, and aesthetics of flute tunes, but rather to a deeper cultural understanding of flute tunes. The study will not only provide a realistic picture of the survival of the flute genre, but will also be able to explore the regularity of the sustainable development of local opera. The study not only depicts the survival of the genre, but also shows the inheritance and transformation of the artistic and social functions of the flute in the midst of historical transition, thus revealing the relationship between the cultural environment and social functions during the historical transformation, thus revealing the symbiotic relationship between the cultural environment and the art form, and providing inspiration and lessons for the inheritance and protection of the flute tune. The study also provides inspiration and reference for the preservation of the flute.

Practical and Theoretical Implications

As we can see from the relevant literature, there is still a lack of documented research on flute tunes. The research results on the flute tune are relatively few. Since there are few research results about the flute tune, this thesis provides a large research space. However, it also means that there is a challenge to conduct an in-depth and systematic study of flute tunes. The relatively abundant research results of the Lingqiu Luoluo cadence provide a rich literature reference for this thesis, which can help to clarify the history of the transmission of the flute tune and analyze the history of the flute tune. It provides an important reference for clarifying the history of the transmission of the flute tune and analyzing whether it is homologous and similar to the Lingqiu Luo Luo cadence, which is also in the Luo Luo cadence family.

Conclusion

Under the impact of today's mass media and new entertainment industries, the traditional folk opera genre of flute tune is facing the existential crisis of extinction. The call for saving, preserving and inheriting the flute tune has become stronger and stronger. In the field of survey, although I can feel from the words and mannerisms of artists such as Fan Fanchangzha, Fan Shanli, Fan Xiyan, Fan Shaojiong, etc. I can feel their deep hope and love for the flute tunes, but, based on the current conditions, can still see the president and members. However, based on the current conditions, it is still possible to see some of the difficulties and helplessness of the president and members. The author hopes that this study will provide some theoretical results for the study of the local folk opera, and provide some theoretical support for the inheritance, revitalization, and sustainable development of the flute tune. It is also hoped that the study will bring the development of the flute tune as an intangible cultural heritage to the attention of the academic community.

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